

Conceptual CAD design of the workstation for XAFS spectroscopy and spectral-domain X-ray OCT studies using a laser plasma X-ray source based on a gas puff target containing micron-sized droplets

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Warsaw, 2023

Graphical projection

Vacuum turbo pump

Vacuum chamber

CCD camera

Optical table

Laser power supply

NL302 Nd:YAG laser

Vacuum rough pumps

Side view

Vacuum turbo pump

Vacuum chamber

CCD camera

Optical table

Laser power supply

NL302 Nd:YAG laser

Vacuum rough pumps

**Setup arrangement for XAFS studies
(Top view)**

**Setup arrangement for XCT studies
(Top view)**

Cutaway diagram

Laser beam

Gas puff valve

Vacuum diaphragm

X-ray optic

Sample

Chamber details

Chamber details

Chamber details

